

Financing Practices of Entrepreneurs in Small and Medium Enterprises in Southwestern Nigeria: An Effectuation Perspective.

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Abstract

This study investigated financing practices of entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Southwestern Nigeria from the perspective of effectuation theory. The study explored the relevance of the effectuation theory as a useful framework to the financing practices of entrepreneurs in established small and medium enterprises. The methodology used to carry out this study was a mixed-method approach. That is, a qualitative approach within a dominant quantitative technique. Four owner-managers who were purposively selected were interviewed in depth, while 748 firms in the study area were surveyed with questionnaire. The tools of analysis, for the data obtained from the personal interview and survey questionnaire were descriptive statistics and effectuation framework logics. Findings revealed that entrepreneurs in SMEs make use of means-driven effectuation logics in their financing practices such as: pre-payment from customers (33.50%), credit purchase from suppliers (51.50%), personal credibility (86.00%), personal reputation (61.00%), experience from previous business activities (80.50%); support from trade associations (55.08) and assistance from competitors (26.00%). The study therefore concludes that SMEs in the South Western Nigeria, make use of effectuation logics in their financing practices and as a result the effectuation theory is a relevant framework to explain financing practices of these entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Financing practices, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs, small and medium enterprises, causation logic, effectuation theory.

July, 2015: This study was funded by TetFund, Nigeria Institutional Based Research Grant.

1.1 Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in many emerging markets and developing countries do not have access to financing (Beck, Demircug-Kunt, and Maksimovic, 2004; Berger and Udell, 2006 and OECD 2006). This is especially worrisome in the sense that SMEs account for a large portion of the labor force, a large portion of enterprises and also a large portion of national income. Moreover, a sizeable portion of the population already earn their living in micro or small and medium enterprises, often earning poor wages, most especially in low income developing countries (OECD 2006). Ayyagari, Beck and Demircug-Kunt (2003) reported that SMES and informal enterprises in low income countries, account for over 60 per cent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and 70 per cent of total employment. In Nigeria, SMEs when combined with micro enterprises contributed 46.54 percent to GDP in nominal terms. A total of 32, 414, 884 persons were employed by the micro enterprises sector as at December 2010. While a total of 39,478 persons were employed in small and medium enterprises, representing 22,139 males (56.08%) and 17,339 females (43.92%) (SMEDAN/NBS, 2012).

In the case of Nigeria, studies (OECD, 2006 and World Bank, 2009) have shown that if environmental challenges are addressed, the SME sector could be made more robust, thereby contributing to poverty alleviation, employment generation and economic growth. Other studies have also suggested that the SMEs in Nigeria are the catalysts for economic growth and development as well as the backbone of the Nation (Ihua, 2009). This notwithstanding, a World Bank study (2009) has shown that low access to financing is the next most important constraint, for Nigeria SMEs after electricity shortage. Thus, a crucial element in the efforts to reduce poverty and generate employment opportunities in the country rests on the capacity of SMEs to have unhindered access to external finance.

In the course of this study, a vast amount of literature discovered on financing practices of SMEs were mostly from developed countries and there appears a dearth of studies on low income developing countries, such as Nigeria for example. This study intends to fill that gap and hope to make a modest contribution to the literature on SMEs

financing practices from the perspective of effectuation in a low income developing country.

SMEs are of critical economic importance, because they are the engines of growth and development for most developed, emerging and developing countries of the world. Lack of finance in the appropriate forms can constitute serious obstacles to growth and development in the sector and consequently, hampers their significant contributions to the economies of these countries (OECD, 2006, Beck and Demirguc-Kunt, 2006). The SME sector in Nigeria is much smaller compared to other developing countries at analogous level of development and economic activities, such as, Brazil, Indonesia and South Africa (World Bank, 2009). The sector is hampered, by financing mainly and an environment that presents considerable challenges like, poor infrastructure, low skills and weak governance (World Bank, 2009). Financing is one of the major determinants of growth and survival of small and medium enterprises in both developing and developed countries, as shown by many studies (UNCTAD, 1995 and SBA, 2008).

A survey (SMEDAN/NBS, 2012) conducted in 2010 shows that financing and financial assistance is considered by 24.7 per cent of the enterprises as the most needed areas of assistance. The same survey also shows that in diagnosing the major problems militating against enterprises' development in Nigeria, lack of access to finance ranks as the most severe. Access to finance ranked first, among the six key constraints facing the sector (SMEDAN/NBS, 2012). Financing access allows SMEs to undertake productive investments, such as expanding their businesses, meet their working capital needs and acquire the latest technologies to enhance their capacities. Poor access to financing can stunt and be a major hindrance to the growth and development of the SME sector (World Bank, 2009). Small and medium enterprises, with the dominance in numbers among operating businesses in any economy and their importance in employment generation and poverty alleviation, have traditionally faced difficulty in accessing financing, particularly external financing in forms of formal credit or equity (Mambula, 2002; Storey and Greene, 2010).

The financing gaps created by lack of access to external financing due to amongst others, information asymmetries can be dampened with the use of other creative methods under bootstrap finance. Theoretical and empirical reviews show different financing practices that are based on traditional institutions or market transactions approaches to fill the gap created by lack of access to external finance. This study intends to explore the possibility of further filling of the financing gap by enhancing the financing practices of SMEs through combining the effectuation model with the traditional causative methods.

The effectuation framework offers an alternative financing practices to the existing paradigm that is goal driven which assumes that SMEs financing practices come from internal and external sources to meet their capital acquisition and working capital needs. This study intends to determine the extent to which the effectuation logics are relevant to financing practices and thus contributes to extant knowledge in SMEs financing practices. Given that previous studies using the effectuation framework (Morrish, 2009; Sarasvathy, 2001) have been in areas of opportunities identification and investment decision making by portfolio entrepreneurs, this study therefore attempts to extend the effectuation model to financing practices of SMEs. Specifically, the study examined whether effectuation theory can be a useful framework to explain the financing practices of SMEs in Southwestern Nigeria?

2.0 Discovery and Creation Theories Perspectives of Entrepreneurial Financing

There are two alternative perspectives in the field of entrepreneurial action research and these are the discovery theory and the creation theory. Alvarez and Barnes (2007), explain that discovery theory assumes that opportunities are objective; that entrepreneurs differ from non entrepreneurs in important ways and that context of decision making is risky. The two scholars further explain that creation theory on the other hand rests on the assumptions: that opportunities are created by entrepreneurs through emergent and repetitive search process; that entrepreneurs and non entrepreneurs differ in behavior ex-post and that the

context of decision making is either ambiguous or uncertain. The two alternative perspectives are applied in the analysis of three entrepreneurship dimensions, such as, entrepreneurial decision-making, business planning process and financing decision of entrepreneurs' ventures. (Alvarez and Barney, 2007)

The financing options under the two alternatives perspectives also vary depending under which of the two models an entrepreneur is operating. Financing under discovery theory is assumed to be external funding from Banks and even venture capital firms because information asymmetric between a firm and its external capital sources is either low or easy to overcome (Sapienza and Gupta, 1994; Admati and Aficidere, 1994). For entrepreneurs operating under creation theory, they do not expect funding from traditional external sources because of problem of information asymmetric. The creation theory financing options rely more on 'Bootstrapping' that is family friends and fools (Bhide, 1992). The information opacity is no problem, because the troika is investing in the entrepreneur ---- his ability to learn, his character, creativity and flexibility---- not in the opportunity an entrepreneur plans to exploit. These essentially are both predicated on "predictive causative model" of enterprise finance. The effectuation framework that is in contention in this study however belongs to the creation school of thoughts in entrepreneurship.

2.1 The Effectuation theory

The theory of effectuation is a contrast to the current causation theory in entrepreneurship. The predictive causative model 'takes a particular effect as given and focus on selecting between means and how to select possible effects that can be created with the given means (Sarasvathy, 2001). Sarasvathy (2001) uses a metaphor of preparing a meal, to clearly explain the effectuation theory, so as to draw out the distinction between the linear predictive causative model and the control and contingency oriented effectuation model. The theory is means-driven and not goal-driven and thereby eliminating the assumption of pre-existing goals. The theory suggests, that creation of artifacts

is a reflection of the entrepreneur's individual situation, in particular, who you are, what you know and whom you know (Sarasvathy, 2001). These three categories are the "means" or resources that entrepreneurs start with, the combination of which determines what types of idea or opportunities they should pursue. These so-called means reflect the entrepreneur's "own traits, tastes and abilities; the knowledge corridors they are in and the social networks they are part of" (Sarasvathy, 2001).

Effectuation framework offers an alternative to the widely use causation logic, where decision makers start with pre-determined goals and gather resources to achieve the goal (Sarasvathy, 2001). Whereas, in effectuation, entrepreneurs start with the resources that are available to them, without pre-determined goals and as a result, outcome may be just one of many possibilities. Effectuation reasoning can therefore, allow entrepreneurs to change and also shape and reconstruct overtime, thereby making use of contingencies as they arise, hence the ability to control the future rather than predict it (Sarasvathy, 2001). Sarasvathy (2001) put forward four principles upon which the theory is predicated and these are:

Affordable loss, rather than expected returns;
Strategic alliances, rather than competitive analyses;
Exploitation of contingencies, rather than pre-existing knowledge and
Control of an unpredictable future, rather than prediction of an uncertain one

However, it must be pointed out, that for both causation and effectuation logics, generalized end goal and aspiration remain the same. The distinguish characteristic is just the choices confronting both models to achieve the generalized end goal or aspiration. The two orientations are, not polar apart as they can complement one another. An entrepreneur can use effectuation logic to create an artifact and then subsequently resorts to rational, causative logic to manage it. Read and Sarasvathy (2005) also note that at a novice stage, entrepreneurs may vary in their use of causal and effectual actions. Intuitively, at the novice stage, an entrepreneur may apply causal logic if he or she has resources to start a venture and vice-versa.

While Sarasvathy built an elegant and useful theory, to some scholars, it is not in itself a complete framework (Berglund, 2007; Kraaijenbrink, 2008). The theory is viewed as more useful in explaining human action and not entrepreneurial process and that the six dimensions on which the two models differ are independent and as such should be the focus of attention instead of the two models (Kraaijenbrink, 2008). This has led scholars from both sides to believe that, combining the two models will offer a better explanation of the entrepreneurial phenomenon (Berglund, 2007; Kraaijenbrink, 2008). This view is not far from Read and Sarasvathy (2005) position expressed above in terms of complementarities of the two models.

In an empirical study conducted by Morrish (2009) on effectuation approach of portfolio entrepreneurs to venture development, there is evidence that the portfolio entrepreneurs made use of effectuation reasoning. The study shows that effectuation reasoning is employed during preliminary and early stages of venture and portfolio development; while the portfolio entrepreneurs employed causation logic as venture and portfolio mature (Morrish, 2009). The findings of Morrish (2009) study further support the position of Read and Sarasvathy (2005) that both causation and effectuation approaches can complement each other. The study however is limited in scope in the sense that only four successful participating entrepreneurs were involved in the case method approach used in the study. A further empirical study using statistical survey method is required for the findings to be generalizable.

3.0 Methodology

3.0.1 The methodology adopted for this study is mixed-method approach. Therefore the approach to the research objective of this study employs triangulation in the methods of data collection and analysis. The qualitative approach is thus an extension of the quantitative analysis of the data conducted on the 748 small and medium enterprises, the objective is to corroborate the analysis of the personal interviews conducted on the

four small and medium enterprises with the results of the quantitative analysis. In a qualitative research, the focus is not on generalization of the findings to the entire population of small and medium enterprises in the Southwestern Nigeria, but to generalize the results to existing theories. The results from the quantitative design using descriptive statistics can be generalized, the qualitative aspect to the research objective is to make the study more robust and find out if the qualitative results can confirm the results of the quantitative analysis.

The data from the personal interview is going to be analysis of textual descriptions using the effectuation logics and the outcomes to be discussed vis-à-vis the result of the earlier quantitative analysis. The data to be analyzed is along the eight dimensions used in quantitative analysis and these are: prepayment from customers; credit purchase from suppliers; personal credibility; one's reputation; trade association assistance; experience from previous business activities, assistance from competitors and assistance from family and friends. These eight dimensions are all logics of effectuation that are means-driven, based on who you are, what you know and who you know, to explore how these logics are employed by small and medium enterprises in their financing practices.

4.0 Results and Discussion

This aspect of this study is to explore the extent to which effectuation framework can be useful to explain the financing practices of small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria. This aspect is divided into two parts; the first part is the descriptive statistics on the data gathered from the 748 small and medium enterprises surveyed. The second aspect is on the qualitative data gathered through personal interview conducted on four enterprises. The results from the two aspects are going to be compared for purposes of literal and analytical generalization of the results.

The descriptive statistics on data from the 748 enterprises gathered from the field work as related to effectuation logics measured use such as: prepayment from customers; credit purchase from suppliers; personal credibility of the entrepreneurs;

the reputation of the entrepreneurs; trade association assistance; experience from previous business activities and assistance from competitors are as presented.

Table 4.1 (Appendix) shows the analysis of data with regards to prepayment (PP) from customers as a financing practice. The results from the table 1 show that 41.85% agree/strongly agree while 39.84% disagree/strongly disagree to this financing practice. The result of this study shows that, 41.85% agree/strongly agree to prepayment from customers as a financing practice when combined with credit purchase from suppliers with 62.71% the average which is 52.28% is stronger than World Bank study (2009) average of 25% in Nigeria. This result also shows a fair evidence of effectuation logics in financing practices of small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria. This alternative financing practice based on who you know which is means-driven, is backed by fair evidence as shown by this study results, that entrepreneurs make use of this effectuation logics in their financing practices. These alternative financing practices provide entrepreneurs who are discouraged from accessing regular financial institutions to meet their financing needs without the restrictions that institutional and market transactions can impose. Table 4.2 also shows the analysis of credit purchase from suppliers (CP) based on the data gathered from the survey conducted on 748 small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria. The findings from table 2 show that 62.71% agree/strongly agree while 24.33% disagree/strongly disagree to this financing practice. This result when combined with the analysis of prepayment for purchase from customers provides an average of 52.28% of respondents agree/strongly agree to this financing practice, which contradicts the result from World Bank study (2009) with an average of 25%. This particular practice is means-driven based on who you know logic of effectuation theory (Sarasvathy, 2001). This result showing 62.71% agree/strongly agree provides a strong evidence that effectuation logics are employed in the financing practices of small and medium enterprises' in South West Nigeria. This should not come as a surprise because 85% of entrepreneurs who would like to secure loans for their enterprises are discouraged from even trying to

get a loan, therefore an alternative approach that is conducted outside of the market or institutional restrictions becomes attractive.

As shown in the data analysis in table 4.3 with regards to the use of one's personal credibility in financing, the result shows that 72.06% agree/strongly agree while 18.85% disagree/strongly disagree to this logic in financing practices. This result thus provides very strong evidence that effectuation logics are employed in financing practices of small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria. The use of one's personal credibility is based on who you are a means-driven approach to financing, regarded as one of the pillars that effectuation theory rests on. When one uses one's credibility to achieve financing needs, effectuation logic is being employed (Sarasvathy, 2001). The attractiveness of using this logic among entrepreneurs in SMEs can be understood against the background that a dismal 1% of SMEs entrepreneurs are able to use financial institutions platform for their financing needs.

Table 4.4 also shows the result of the analysis on data gathered from the field survey with regards to the use of one's reputation in financing practices of owner-managers of small and medium enterprises. The results from the table 4 show that 71.53% agree/strongly agree while 19.11% disagree/strongly disagree to this financing practice. This result with 71.53% agree/strongly agree to this practice is a very strong indication that the owner-managers of these small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria are making use of effectuation logics in their financing practices. The use of one's reputation is based on who you are a pillar that effectuation theory rests on (Sarasvathy, 2001). This alternative approach that is means-driven provides SMEs with financing that free them from market transaction costs and institutional requirements for similar financing.

As shown in table 4.5, the analysis of data gathered from the field survey also shows that 55.08% agree/strongly agree while 31.21% disagree/strongly disagree to the use of trade association assistance in financing practices. This result shows fairly strong evidence that effectuation logics are employed by

the owner-managers of these small and medium enterprises surveyed in this study. The use of trade association assistance in financing practices is an effectuation logic based on who you know which is one of the strong bases of effectuation theory (Sarasvathy, 2001). The Effectuation theory is built on principle of alliance as opposed to competition that causation framework rests (Sarasvathy, 2001). As shown in table 4.6, on the analysis of data gathered from the field survey, 60.56% agree/strongly agree while 25.81% disagree/strongly disagree on the use of experience from previous business activities in financing practices. The use of previous business experience is also effectuation logic based on what you know, that is, your knowledge corridor and previous deliberate practice. This finding is a strong indication of effective employment of effectuation logics in financing practices of owner-managers of these small and medium enterprises in South West Nigeria. The use of one's knowledge corridor based on experience from previous business activities, is one of the principles upon which effectuation theory is based (Read and Sarasvathy, 2005).

Table 4.7, also shows the results in relation to use of effectuation logics, that is, how assistance from competitors can be employed in financing practices. The finding from analysis of data of owner-managers surveyed in this study shows that 27.0% agree/strongly agree while 57.08% disagree/strongly disagree on the use of this logic on financing practices. The effectuation theory is premised on the principle of seeking cooperation as against the causation logics, of competition (Sarasvathy, 2001). That is, cooperation is one of the principles of effectuation. However the practice of using assistance of competitors for financing is weak.

As shown in Table 4.8 all the interviewees are male and their ages range from 34 years to 56 years, this age bracket is considered as the middle age group that constitutes the majority of Nigeria population (NPC, 2006), with 60%. The average number of years of business experience of the four interviewees is ten years which is sufficient for them to understand the nature of questions asked and for one to expect accurate in their responses.

The owner managers of these small and medium enterprises are well educated. Three out of the four interviewees have tertiary education background with two out of the three possessing a Ph.D. degree. Only one out of the three interviewees has a basic secondary school education. The ownership structure is 50% sole proprietorship and 50% partnership; this is not out of place with the findings in the ownership structure of the 748 small and medium enterprises surveyed, where the majority of the enterprises are sole proprietorship.

The table 4.8 also shows that each of the interviewee has at the least two enterprises under his ownership, which means that the interviewees are all portfolio entrepreneurs which fits one of the features of the purposive sampling technique chose for this qualitative study, that the interviewee must have more than one business. The four interviewees are all located in the Osogbo/Ibadan axis for the convenience of the researcher. The assets value of all the four enterprises falls within #10million to #30million which means they can all be considered as small enterprises based on SMEDAN/NBS (2012) definition of small and medium enterprises. The number of employees also ranges from 15 to 23 employees, based on the SMEDAN/NBS definition of small and medium enterprises, the four owner-managers enterprises can also be classified as small enterprises.

Table 4.9 shows that only one of the interviewees engaged in the use of prepayments from customers in his financing practices. This result shows that the prepayments from customer which is means-driven approach based on whom you know logic of effectuation theory is not prevalent among the interviewees. The textual description of one of the respondents goes thus:

Participant 4

"It plays a significant role because if you don't pay back, you might not be granted another credit. Very important and since I started, some credits that I took even before I started are being aid gradually on the terms we agreed on".

This result which is 25% of the interviewees admitting to the use of this logic, also shows evidence that the logic is employed by SMEs in

Southwestern Nigeria, though not a strong evidence when compared with the 41.85 percent evidence from table 4.9 of the 748 enterprises surveyed in the quantitative analysis. Both figures are evidence but not strong evidence in support of this particular effectuation logic in explaining financing practices of SMEs.

As shown in Table 4.9, the analysis of data of the interviewees also shows that a considerable number of the owner-managers employ use of credit purchase from suppliers in their financing practices. This can be translated into 50% of the interviewees using this means-driven approach based on who you know to drive their financing practices, which is one of the logics of effectuation theory (Sarasvathy, 2001). This result is not far off from the result from the quantitative survey of the 748 small and medium enterprises with 62.71% (see Table 9) agree/strongly agree to this technique in their financing practices. The textual descriptions from three of the four participants in the personal interview conducted are as presented below:

Participant 1

"We are to pay. From the place that we are buying the product, they are not giving us the room to buy by credit, they will increase the price but it is advisable for us to buy and carry lower price"

Participant 3

"We have lots credit purchase from different companies, they'll bring market maybe two or three week, some a month before we repay for the credit"

Participant 4

"There is no credit since I pay for everything I buy upfront and I use my personal expertise to make sure that the rice is at the barest minimum and I was not swindle while trying to grow or while trying to establish the business"

The results from both the quantitative and qualitative analysis with 62.71% and 50% respectively are strong evidence that small and medium enterprises in Southwestern Nigeria employ this technique considered as effectuation logic in their financing practices. These results from both quantitative and qualitative analyses contradict the World Bank (2009) results that show 25% of SMEs making use of this financing practice. Therefore the result of the qualitative analysis confirms the result of the quantitative analysis. The

strong evidence this study provides on the use of credit purchase from suppliers, is expected to fill financing gap occasioned by the fact that many SMEs are discouraged in accessing external financing. A dismal 1% can only access the external financing despite the fact that 85 percent of SMEs would like to access but are discouraged because of banks requirements that may be hard to meet by these entrepreneurs (World Bank, 2009). This effectuation technique becomes an attractive financing alternative to external financing and can augment the internal financing options open to SMEs.

The results from Table 4.9 also show that all the interviewees engage in the use of one's personal credibility in financing practices. This result translates into 100%. This result also confirms the result from the quantitative analysis with 72.06%. Therefore these two results provide strong evidence that small and medium enterprises in the Southwest make use of this financing logic which is means-driven based on who you are a principle of effectuation theory (Sarasvathy, 2001). The attractiveness of owner-managers in deploying this logic in their financing practices can be understood against the background that 85% of the entrepreneurs would like access to external finance as represented by banks but are discouraged due to hard requirements by banks that are difficult for the enterprises to meet (World Bank, 2009). Therefore the logic of effectuation by way of personal credibility to attract financing provides an alternative to market/institutional based financing practices.

The results from Table 4.9 based on analysis of data provided by the interviewees, show that 50% engage in the use of one owns reputation in their financing practices. This result and that of 71.53% result of the quantitative analysis of 748 enterprises surveyed in Southwestern Nigeria provide strong evidence that owner-managers of enterprises are making use of this logic. Use of one's own reputation in financing is an effectuation logic based on who you are (Sarasvathy, 2001). The strong evidence provided by the results of both quantitative and qualitative analyses, show that the owner-managers are employing effectuation logics

in their financing practices as an alternative and augmentation of both internal and external financing practices.

As shown from the analysis of data provided by the interviewees, only one of the interviewee indicated that his trade association assists in his financing. The textual descriptions of the respondents on this question go thus:

Participant 1

"They are not involved. Even when the time that they want to be involved they add burden into the business that if the person can work hard in order to make the record and the achievement of a thing to be worked out perfectly, they can roll out the business in order to go to the bank. So, based on that, the association has not even played a role in the business".

Participant 2

"They give us assistance, at times, they will load petrol for us and later we pay them back".

This can be translated into 25% of the respondents. The figure from the quantitative analysis of 748 small and medium enterprises surveyed with 55.08% is better than the qualitative figure 25%. However, both provide evidence of these entrepreneurs making use of this effectuation logic based on who you know with emphasis on cooperation and alliances building instead of competition logic of causation theory. These results from both quantitative and qualitative analyses show evidence though not strong, but at the least it establishes the use of this logic in financing practices. Therefore the method shows that this effectuation logic is employed by entrepreneurs in their financing practices as an alternative financing technique.

Also, Table 4.9 shows that all the interviewees use their experience from previous business activities to drive their financing practices. These results translate into 100%. This result confirms the 60.56% of the respondents surveyed in the quantitative analysis admitting to the use of their experience from previous business activities. The textual descriptions of two respondents on use of experience from previous business activities are expressed as follows:

Participant 3

"No businessman can do without that. I have gone round Nigeria; the oyinbo people say that travelling is part of education. I gathered experience from different art of the state to improve my experience, what they do in Lagos and other places, maybe in Osogbo it's not done, so I acquired all those knowledge and materialize it and use it perfectly".

Participant 4

"The past experience in business world really helped me, but that experience that I first use in getting the structure down and after that educational background then came in because in consulting with the ministry in registration of the school, in recruiting teachers, so my academic helped along that line".

Use of experience from previous business activities that is means-driven based on what you know as a result of your knowledge corridor and deliberate practice, which are principles of effectuation theory. The findings from analyses of both quantitative and qualitative data are strong evidence that entrepreneurs make use of this effectuation logic that provides an alternative financing technique to fill financing gaps arising from failings of market and institutional financing of SMEs.

As shown from Table 4.9 all but one of the interviewees agree to the use of assistance from competitors in their financing practices, this result translates into 25%. This result confirms the result from the qualitative analysis of 748 small and medium enterprises with 27.00% of the respondents agree/strongly agree to the use of this effectuation logic. The results from both approaches provide weak evidence but it is employed. This particular effectuation logic is premised on the principle of cooperation instead of competition preached by causation logic.

Conclusion

The results from this study provide strong evidence in support of use of effectuation logics in financing practices of small and medium enterprises in Southwestern Nigeria. The findings from the quantitative aspect of the survey of 748 entrepreneurs in SMEs show the following distributions in how they make use of effectuation logics: Prepayments from customers – 42%; credit

purchase from suppliers – 63%; personal credibility – 72% Use of one’s reputation – 72%; Trade Association Assistance – 55%; Experience from previous Business Activities – 61% and Assistance from competitors – 27%. These results are strong indications that entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises make use of this means-driven approach in their financing practices.

The findings from the qualitative data, using personal interview to explore the use of effectuation logics, also show the following in terms of how they employ effectuation logics in their financing practices: Prepayments from customers – 25%; credit purchase from suppliers – 50%; personal credibility – 100%; one’s reputation – 50%; Trade association assistance – 25%; experience from previous business activities – 100% and assistance from competitors – 25%. These results from qualitative data confirm the results from the quantitative data and therefore the results emanating from the two methods are consistent with one and another. Therefore, it can be confirmed based on the analyses of the data from quantitative survey and personal interview, that small and medium enterprises in South Western Nigeria make use of effectuation logics in their financing practices. Consequently, it can be said that effectuation theory is a relevant framework that can be used to explain the financing practices of entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises in the study area.

The results from this study with regards to effectuation logics has shown that small and medium enterprises owner-managers, make use of effectuation logics in their financing practices. The study has shown strong evidence in support of effectuation logics along all the dimensions that were tested in this study. Therefore, this study has shown that the means-driven approach to financing are used by owner-managers of small and medium enterprises in South Western Nigeria and as a consequence the effectuation theory becomes relevant framework to explain the financing practices of these enterprises.

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APPENDIX

Table 4.1: Prepayment from Customers

Prepayment from Customers	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	133	17.78	17.78
Disagree	165	22.06	39.84
Don't Know	137	18.32	58.16
Agree	251	33.56	91.71
Strongly Agree	62	8.29	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.2: Credit Purchase from Suppliers

Credit Purchase from Suppliers	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	86	11.50	11.50
Disagree	96	12.83	24.33
Don't Know	97	12.97	37.30
Agree	370	49.47	86.76
Strongly Agree	99	13.24	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.3: Personal Credibility of SMEs Entrepreneurs

Personal Credibility	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	72	9.63	9.63
Disagree	69	9.22	18.85
Don't Know	68	9.09	27.94
Agree	420	56.15	84.09
Strongly Agree	119	15.91	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.4: The Reputation of SMEs Entrepreneurs

One's Reputation	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	69	9.22	9.22
Disagree	74	9.89	19.12
Don't Know	70	9.36	28.48
Agree	414	55.35	83.82
Strongly Agree	121	16.18	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.5: Trade Association Assistance for SMEs Entrepreneurs

Trade Association Assistance	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	106	14.17	14.17
Disagree	120	16.04	30.21
Don't Know	110	14.71	44.92
Agree	320	42.78	87.70
Strongly Agree	92	12.30	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.6: Experience from Previous Business Activities of SMEs Entrepreneurs

Experience from Previous Business Activities	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	72	9.63	9.63
Disagree	121	16.18	25.80
Don't Know	102	13.64	39.44
Agree	346	46.26	85.70
Strongly Agree	107	14.30	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.7: Assistance from Competitors of SMEs Entrepreneurs

Assistance from Competitors	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Strongly Disagree	296	39.57	39.57
Disagree	131	17.51	57.09
Don't Know	119	15.91	72.99
Agree	160	21.39	94.39
Strongly Agree	42	5.61	100.00
Total	748	100.00	

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.8: Personal/Business Characteristics of Interviewees

Participants	Gender	Age	Years in Business	Education Level	Ownership Legal Structure	No of Business	No of Employers	Asset Value
1	Male	34	8yrs	Ph.D./MBA	Sole proprietorship	3	23	#12m
2	Male	52	15yrs	High School	Private limited company	3	20	#10m
3	Male	56	15yrs	BA/B.Sc.	Partnership	2	15	#12m
4	Male	51	3	Ph.D.	Partnership	2	18	#30m

Source: Field Survey, 2015.

Table 4.9: Effectuation Logics Employed by SMEs Entrepreneurs

Effectuation Logics	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4
Prepayments from customers	-	-	-	√
Credit purchase from suppliers	-	√	√	-
Personal credibility	√	√	√	√
One's reputation	-	√	√	-
Trade association assistance	-	√	-	-
Experience from previous business activities	√	√	√	√
Assistance from competitors	-	√	-	-
Assistance from family and friend	-	√	-	√

Source: Field Survey, 2015.